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MUNDARIJA

“Yashil” iqtisodiyotga jadal o‘tish va barqaror texnologik o‘zgarishlar provard maqsadlarimiz	12
Abduraxmonova Gulnora Kalandarovna	
Noqonuniy sigaretalar hajmini Empty pack survey hamda Gap analysis usullari yordamida aniqlash (O‘zbekiston Respublikasi misolida)	17
Sanjar Mirzaliev, Bobur Qoraboev, Surmaniso Mirzalieva	
Raqamli transformatsiya sharoitida bank xizmat turlarini rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	22
A. R. Norov, N. N. Norova	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot rivojida tijorat banklari kapitalini takomillashtirish istiqbollari	28
Norov Akmal Ruzimamatovich	
Ishsizlik darajasini kamaytirish yo‘lidagi strategik yondashuv: tadbirkorlikka o‘rgatish va kasbiy tayyorlash	33
Bakiyeva Iroda Akbarovna, Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich	
Meva-sabzavot mahsulotlarini eksportga yo‘naltirishda standart talablariga uyg‘unlashtirishni baholash va uni amalga oshirish yo‘llari	42
Xojiyev Elshod Yoqub o‘g‘li	
Investitsiyalarni jalb qilishda foyda solig‘idan foydalanish	50
Zarif Oripovich Axrorov	
Mamlakat iqtisodiy o‘shish va rivojlanishida xorijiy investitsiyalarning roli	55
Akishova Shaxnoza Davlet qizi	
O‘zbekiston sharoitida “yashil” iqtisodiyotni joriy etish istiqbollari: nazariya va amaliyot.....	60
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o‘g‘li	
Aksiyadorlik jamiyatlari faoliyatini takomillashtirish yo‘nalishlari.....	65
Sadikova Muslima Alisher qizi	
Mehnat bozorida aholi bandligini oshirishning zamonaviy usullari	70
Xuvaydullaeva Iroda Xusniddin qizi	
Ichki turizmni rivojlantirishning tashkiliy mexanizmining asosiy prinsiplari	76
Isomiddinov Inomjon Qurbonali o‘g‘li	
Yengil sanoat korxonalarida ichki audit jarayonlari va uning samaradorligini oshirish istiqbollari.....	79
Maxmudov A.N.	
Ishlab chiqarish resurslaridan foydalangan holda korporativ boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirish	86
Karimov Akramjon Ikromjon o‘g‘li	
Kredit foiz stavkalari va unga ta‘sir etuvchi omillar tahlili.....	92
Orifova Dilnoza Obid qizi	
O‘zbekistonda hayot sug‘urtasini rivojlantirish yo‘llari	97
Jamolova Xonzoda O‘rolboy qizi	
Soliqqa Tortishning Mohiyati va Uni Iqtisodiyotdagi Ahamiyati.....	102
Ruziyev Shaxzod Behzod o‘g‘li, Togayev Salim Sobirovich	
Raqamli texnologiyalarning oziq-ovqat sanoatini rivojlantirishdagi ta‘siri	110
Abduraxmanova Zuxra Toxir qizi	
O‘zbekistonda sog‘lomlashtirish turizmini rivojlantirishda inson resurslarining o‘rni.....	115
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	
Biznes jarayonlarining samaradorligini baholash ko‘rsatkichlarini muvofiqlashtirish usullari.....	121
Abdusalomova Nodira Baxodirovna	

Turizmda inson resurslarini rivojlantirishning nazariy asoslari.....	126
J. Mansurov	
Hududiy turizm rivojlanishining iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirishda zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalarini qo'llanilishi.....	131
Dustmurodov Orifjon Ismatilloevich	
Aholi ixtiyoridagi resurslarni jalb qilish orqali aholi turmush darajasini oshirish.....	138
Jo'raeva Shahlo Uchqun qizi	
Turistik xizmatlarning samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish.....	141
Abduvohidov Abdumalik Mahkamovich	
Xo'jalik subyektlarining moliyaviy salohiyatini mustahkamlash va moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlashni uslubiy jihatlari.....	146
Xasanov Baxodir Akramovich, Akramov G'olibjon Bahodir o'g'li	
Mahsulot raqobatbardoshligini baholash usullari va ulardan foydalanish muammolari.....	153
Onorboev Sh.M.	
Loyihalarni Islom modeli asosida moliyalashtirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	159
Aminova Nilufar Umarboy qizi	
O'zbekiston tijorat banklarida foiz riskini boshqarish tizimini takomillashtirish.....	167
Isakov Janabay Yakipbaevich	
Ayollar inson kapitalini rivojlantirishning ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy ahamiyati.....	174
S.A.Bozorova, M.M.Xolmatov	
Qayta tiklanuvchi energiya manbalarini yaratish bilan bog'liq loyihalarni moliyalashtirish.....	179
Shaislamova Nargiza Kabilovna	
Effectiveness of using blockchain technologies in cash flow audit in enterprises of the republic of Uzbekistan.....	188
Atamurodov Saidmurad Yakhyoyevich	
Loan portfolio of banks in Uzbekistan and ways to improve the efficiency of loan portfolio management.....	196
Avazkhon Agzamov, Dilrabo Malikova	
Digitization of the economy and its role in enhancing bank stability and reducing poverty.....	201
Kholiyorov Murod Kahramon ugli, Kholiyorova Shokhista Kahramon kizi	
Directions for sustainable development of tourism in the namangan region of Uzbekistan.....	204
Khusniddin Egamnazarov	
Improving comprehensive monitoring of cash flows in the treasury through intelligent information fusion systems applications.....	208
Shodmonkulova Shahlo	
Importance of staff service quality at uzbek halal restaurants in Uzbekistan.....	214
Shodiyona Sanginova	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida barqaror turizmni iqtisodiy rivojlantirishda hunarmandchilikning o'rni.....	220
Xushnazarova Maxzuna Gulamdjanovna	
Mamlakat turizmini barqaror rivojlanishida mice turizmining ahamiyati.....	226
Xalimova Fayyoza Nafasovna	
Ways to expand the position of the light industrial enterprise in the yarn and knitwear market.....	231
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Agzamov Avazkhon Talgatovich	
Improvement of methodology of accounting and analysis of included financial statements and investments in subsidiary societies.....	238
Nasirkhodjaeva Dilafruz Sabitkhanovna	

Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida investitsiyalar: barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishning muhim omili.....	254
Amonova Nazokat Uturovna	
O'zbekiston respublikasi korxonalarida pul oqimlari auditida blokchain texnologiyalaridan foydalanish samaradorligi.....	259
Atamurodov Saidmurod Yaxyoyevich	
Iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish sharoitida o'zbekistonda turizm xizmatlar iste'molini oshirishning ekonometrik tahlili	267
Dehqonov Burxon Rustamovich	
Agrar soha korxonalarining moliyaviy barqarorligini ta'minlash masalalari.....	278
Erkinxojiyev I.	
Yengil sanoat korxonalarida marketing jarayonlarini tashkil etishning xorij tajribasi	283
Bazarova Fayoza Tuxtamurodovna	
Fiskal siyosatni rivojlantirishda "yashil" budjet daromadlarini o'rganish.....	287
Meyliyev O.R., Gofurova K.	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot: raqamli transformatsiyaning yashil shaharlarning iqtisodiy o'sishiga ta'siri.....	293
Xotamov Ibodulla, Najmiddinov Yahyo	
Buxoro viloyatining kichik va o'rta biznesdagi o'rni, viloyatdagi tumanlar faoliyatidan kelib chiqib hududlarni toifalarga ajratish.....	301
Bozorov Ilyos Isomiddinovich	
Xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlarda ishlab chiqarishning optimal hajmi tahlili	306
Qlichev Baxtiyor Pardaevich, Xoldorov Sardor Umarovich	
Toshkent viloyati fermer xo'jaliklari faoliyatining samaradorligini tanlanma kuzatuvlar asosida statistik tadqiq etish	313
Murodov Jahongir Choriyevich	
O'zbekiston Respublikasida sanoat tarmog'i faoliyati samaradorligini statistik baholashning ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	316
To'raeva Zilola Turg'unovna	
"Yashil" sanoat siyosati – ekologik xavfsizlikni ta'minlashning ustuvor vositasi	320
Muqimov Sherali Axmadali o'g'li	
Raqamli biznes marketingida yashil buxgalteriya hisobining roli: barqaror rivojlanish nuqtai nazaridan qarash.....	327
Allayarov Shamsiddin Amanullayevich, Iskandarov Xurshid Iskandarovich, Yoqubov Madaminbek Abdurahim o'g'li	
Fiskal barqarorlikni ta'minlashda "natijaga yo'naltirilgan budjetlashtirish" uslubidan foydalanish imkoniyatlari.....	333
Kasimova Gulyar Axmatovna, Agzamov Avazxon Talgatovich	
Регулирование занятости и управление трудовыми ресурсами в сфере туризма.....	339
Адылова Зулфия Джавдатовна, Тухтаева Хуршида Фарходовна	
Семь IPO и SPO в экономической истории узбекистана: достижения, проблемы и выводы	346
Чинкулов Кахрамон Равшанович	
Совершенствование учета затрат на производство и калькуляция себестоимости продукции	355
Омонов Шердор Ойбек угли	
Areas of effective use of marketing in the development of foreign economic relations	360
Akhmedov Ikram Akramovich	
Sanoatda oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashning iqtisodiy masalalari	367
Ismoilova Gulchiroy Tolliboy qizi	

Hududlarni iqtisodiy rivojlanishida investitsiyalar ko'rsatkichi tahlili (Sirdaryo viloyati misolida)	373
Karimqulov Jasur Imomboyevich, Alimova Dilafro'z Tohir qizi	
Raqamli transformatsiya davridagi iqtisodiy o'sishga to'rtinchi sanoat inqilobining ta'siri.....	381
Mirxamidova Zahinabonu Mirxamid qizi	
Investitsion muhit va uning hududlarni iqtisodiyot va ijtimoiy rivojlanishdagi ahamiyati.....	388
Muxamadjanov Shaxriyor Solidjon o'g'li	
Portfel investisiya loyihalarini kreditlashni takomillashtirish.....	395
Ibragimov Gafurjan Axmetovich	
O'zbekistonda kapital bozorini rivojlantirish masalalari	401
Turdieva Uzayda Omirbaevna	
Korxonalarining tashqi savdo faoliyatini rivojlantirishda tijorat banklari faolligini oshirish yo'llari.....	408
Ibragimov Mansur Axmetovich	
Methodological foundations of the quality management system in construction industry enterprises.....	414
Usmanov Ilkhom Achilovich, Buriyev Xakim Toshimovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligini rivojlantirish jarayonini ekonometrik modellashtirishda xorijiy davlatlar tajribasining ahamiyati.....	419
Butanova Dilnoza Rustamovna	
O'zbekistonda qishloq turizmini rivojlantirishda Janubiy Koreya tajribasini o'rganish.....	423
Agzamova Nargiza Gapurovna	
Kimyo sanoatiga innovatsiyalarni joriy etish bo'yicha rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasi.....	427
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich	
Концептуальные основы и перспективы развития деятельности кадастровых служб республики узбекистан на основе интеллектуальных технологий	430
М.К. Валиев, А.Х. Абдуллаев, А.Р. Марахимов, Б.М. Ахмедов	
Mahalliy avtomobil benzini tarkibidagi uglevodorod fraksiyalariga ekstragentlarining ta'sirini o'rganish	435
Maxmudov Muxtor Jamolovich, Murtazaev Feruzbek Ismatovich	
Oliy ta'lim muassalaridagi davlat xaridlari tizimining takomillashishi.....	441
Atamuratova Nilufar Yaxshigeldiyevna	
Tijorat banki daromadlari – moliyaviy barqarorlikning omili sifatida.....	446
Umarov Davron Shavkatovich	

DIGITIZATION OF THE ECONOMY AND ITS ROLE IN ENHANCING BANK STABILITY AND REDUCING POVERTY

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Abstract: In the context of economic digitization, strengthening banks' solvency, ensuring their stability and security, and thereby improving the standard of living of the population and reducing poverty are essential reforms to be implemented in the country's economy. The article identifies current problems related to the role of banks in the digitization of the economy and develops scientific proposals aimed at solving these problems.

Key words: Banking and financial system, capitalization level, poverty level, remote banking services, online microcredits, low standard of living, E-Banking and M-Banking.

Annotatsiya: Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida banklarning to'lov qobiliyatini mustahkamlash, ularning barqarorligi va xavfsizligini ta'minlash, shu orqali aholining turmush darajasini yaxshilash va qashshoqlikni kamaytirish mamlakat iqtisodiyotida amalga oshirilishi lozim bo'lgan muhim islohotlardir. Ushbu maqolada iqtisodiyotning raqamlashtirilishida banklarning roli bilan bog'liq hozirgi muammolar aniqlanadi va ushbu muammolarni hal qilishga qaratilgan ilmiy takliflar ishlab chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Bank va moliya tizimi, kapitalizatsiya darajasi, qashshoqlik darajasi, masofaviy bank xizmatlari, onlayn mikrokreditlar, past turmush darajasi, E-banking va M-banking.

Аннотация: В условиях цифровизации экономики важными реформами, которые необходимо реализовать в экономике страны, являются укрепление платежеспособности банков, обеспечение их стабильности и безопасности, что, в свою очередь, способствует повышению уровня жизни населения и сокращению бедности. В статье выявляются актуальные проблемы, связанные с ролью банков в цифровизации экономики, и разрабатываются научные предложения, направленные на их решение.

Ключевые слова: Банковская и финансовая система, уровень капитализации, уровень бедности, дистанционные банковские услуги, онлайн микрокредиты, низкий уровень жизни, E-Banking и M-Banking.

INTRODUCTION

In today's rapidly developing world, the reforms aimed at improving and strengthening the banking and financial system in our country have allowed for an increase in banks' capitalization level, an expansion in the scope of economic lending, an increase in the spectrum of banking services offered, and an enhancement in the role of the banking system in economic development. It should be noted that the reforms undertaken to improve and strengthen our country's banking and financial system have facilitated an increase in banks' capitalization level, an expansion in the scope of economic lending, an increase in the spectrum of banking services offered, and an enhancement in the role of the banking system in economic development.

At the same time, improving the quality of banking services and establishing full-fledged cooperation with business entities remain pressing tasks. In the context of economic digitization, increased stability of the banking system and improved service quality certainly have an impact on reducing poverty levels in countries. In recent years, we have witnessed significant successes in the global fight against poverty, with millions of people escaping poverty through economic growth, social programs, and innovative changes.

Furthermore, the evolution of financial inclusion indices reflects increasing access to financial services, even in remote or under-served areas. The advent of digitization has played a crucial role in this transformation. The development of digital inclusive finance, such as remote banking services, online microcredits, and remote loans provided by private investors, has democratized access to financial services. Digital technologies have enabled financial institutions to reach lower-income populations, providing them with tools to manage their financial lives and engage in economic activities that were previously beyond their reach. In many

regions, especially in developing countries, digital financial inclusion has not only helped reduce poverty but also expanded economic opportunities and supported social inclusion. Poverty reduction strategies, growth in financial inclusion, and the synergy of digital innovations represent a promising triad that continues to shape global economic development and offers avenues for further research and policy formation [1].

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The digitization of the economy has emerged as a key factor in strengthening bank stability and fostering economic development, particularly in developing nations. Digital technologies have reshaped financial services, offering enhanced access, improving operational efficiency, and supporting financial inclusion. Scholars such as Joseph Stiglitz (2019) argue that digitization reduces transaction costs and improves the transparency of financial operations, helping mitigate risks and improve efficiency in the banking sector.

In Uzbekistan, the digitization of the economy is becoming central to modernizing the financial sector. Uzbek economist Sh. Iskandarov highlights that the development of digital banking services in Uzbekistan has directly contributed to improving the stability of banks by increasing their efficiency and risk management capacities. He emphasizes that innovations such as mobile banking, online payments, and digital credit scoring are particularly crucial in reaching underserved populations, thus playing a significant role in reducing poverty through greater financial inclusion (Iskandarov, 2021). Iskandarov's work underscores how digitization fosters a more stable banking environment while simultaneously enabling broad-based access to essential financial resources.

Other international scholars, such as Raghuram Rajan (2018), discuss how digitization can help improve the asset quality of banks by providing advanced tools for credit risk assessment. Rajan asserts that digital platforms allow for real-time monitoring of financial transactions, reducing the potential for fraud and regulatory non-compliance, thereby strengthening the overall stability of banking systems. Furthermore, the application of big data analytics and artificial intelligence (AI) in banking offers more accurate risk predictions and improves decision-making.

In terms of poverty reduction, economist Abhijit Banerjee (2019) explores how digital financial services—such as mobile banking and fintech solutions—enable financial inclusion for low-income populations. By improving access to savings, credit, and insurance services, digital platforms empower individuals and small businesses to manage financial risks more effectively, ultimately contributing to poverty reduction and economic empowerment, particularly in rural areas.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the implementation of these research works, widely used methods in scientific research methodology were used. The use of deductive or inductive methods in the order from generality to individuality and vice versa is effective in studying the subject, and the method of abstract-logical thinking is important in the systematic analysis of the process. In the process of scientific analysis, these scientific research methods observation, generalization, grouping, comparison, analysis, and synthesis and analysis methods were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The digitization of the economy has become one of the most significant developments in modern banking, transforming traditional financial systems and contributing to overall economic growth. Digitization encompasses a broad range of technologies such as mobile banking, online payment systems, blockchain, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics, all of which have a profound impact on the stability of banks and the reduction of poverty.

Digitization plays a crucial role in enhancing the stability of banking institutions. One of the primary ways it does this is by increasing operational efficiency. With the use of automated systems and digital platforms, banks can process transactions faster, reduce human errors, and lower operational costs. Technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) are used to automate processes like credit scoring, fraud detection, and risk assessment, providing more accurate and real-time decision-making tools for banks. This leads to improved risk management, as banks can better monitor credit risks and predict potential defaults.

Another key factor in improving bank stability is the increased transparency and security that digital platforms offer. Blockchain technology, for instance, ensures the immutability and traceability of financial transactions, reducing the likelihood of fraud and improving regulatory compliance. Digital platforms also enable banks to maintain real-time surveillance of their transactions, thereby enhancing accountability and trust within the banking system.

Despite insufficient data for quantitative analysis, recent studies (Banna and Alam 2021; Khera et al. 2021)

have attempted to create composite indicators of developed financial institutions based on related variables. However, these composite indicators have limited sample size [3]. Additionally, annual data on poverty conditions are not always available in many countries, making it challenging to analyze the impact of developed financial institutions on poverty using these indicators. Consequently, empirical research often resorts to proxy indicators, with a focus on mobile phone subscriptions. The primary reason is the extensive availability of data on mobile phone subscriptions, which are crucial for accessing digital financial services.

The following model is proposed to analyze the individual and interactive effects of digital financial inclusion and international remittances on poverty conditions in developing countries [4]:

$$POV_{i,t} = \beta_0 POV_{i,t-1} + \beta_1 DFI_{i,t} + \beta_2 REM_{i,t} + \beta_3 DFI_{i,t} \times REM_{i,t} + \gamma' X_{i,t} + \alpha_i + u_{i,t} \quad (1)$$

here:

- (POV_{i,t}) is the measure of poverty conditions in country (i) at time (t),
- (DFI_{i,t}) is the measure of digital financial inclusion in country (i) at time (t)
- (REM_{i,t}) is the flow of remittances in country (i) at time (t),
- (X_{i,t}) is the vector of control variables in country (i) at time (t),
- (α_i) represents country-specific fixed effects,
- (u_{i,t}) is the error term at time (t) in country (i).

The most important independent variable in this study is DFI, measured by the number of mobile phone subscriptions per 100 people. Remittance flow (REM) is another crucial independent variable, defined as the amount of personal remittances received divided by GDP. It is anticipated that an increase in remittances will help reduce poverty by providing additional income for consumption, investment, or savings to families in their home countries. Therefore, the coefficient for REM in the equation is expected to be negative.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on previous research, this study explores whether digital financial services, mobile communication, and international remittances affect poverty in developing countries individually and interactively.[5] The models explaining poverty levels include mobile phone subscriptions, remittance flows, their interaction duration, and other standard control variables used in the literature. Digital transformation in financial services provides significant opportunities for customers, increases financial activity, and helps expand economic opportunities for clients. One of the prospects of digital banks is the reduction of service costs by 40-60%, as well as saving customers' time and resources associated with visiting the bank and completing paperwork.

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